

اللَّهُمَّ اجْعَلْهُمُ
مِنْ رَحْمَتِكَ

One Day Workshop on

Research Tools:
Supporting Research
and Publication

One-day workshop on:

**Research Tools: Supporting Research and
Publication**

Available online at: <http://dx.doi.org/10.6084/m9.figshare.1293447>

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www.researcherid.com/rid/C-2414-2009

<http://scholar.google.com/citations>

Abstract

- “[Research Tools](#)” can be defined as vehicles that broadly facilitate research and related activities. Scientific tools enable researchers to collect, organize, analyze, visualize and publicized research outputs. Dr. Nader has collected over 700 tools that enable students to follow the correct path in research and to ultimately produce high-quality research outputs with more accuracy and efficiency. It is assembled as an interactive Web-based mind map, titled “[Research Tools](#)”, which is updated periodically.
- “[Research Tools](#)” consists of a hierarchical set of nodes. It has four main nodes: (1) [Searching the literature](#), (2) [Writing a paper](#), (3) [Targeting suitable journals](#), and (4) [Enhancing visibility and impact of the research](#), and six auxiliary nodes. Several free tools can be found in the child nodes. Some paid tools are also included. In this workshop some tools as examples from the four main nodes will be described. The e-skills learned from the workshop are useful across various research disciplines and research institutions.

Problem statements

The search can be time consuming and sometimes tedious task. How can make it easier? How do deal with situations such as:

- “I just join as a new postgraduate student and I am not sure how to do a literature search”
- “I have been in research for some time now but I spend a lot of time to get the articles I want”
- “I am sure I have downloaded the article but I am not able to find it”
- “I wanted to write a new paper, how can I manage the references in the shortest possible time?”
- “I have many references, some of my old papers, and some of my current research. Sometimes, they are so many that I can’t recall where I have kept them in my folders!”
-
- “I have written an article and I am not able to find a proper Journal”
- "I want to increase the citation of my papers, how do I do?"

Objectives

The seminar seeks to serve the following objectives:

- i. To help students who seek to reduce the search time by expanding the knowledge of researchers to more effectively use the "tools" that are available through the Net.
- ii. To evaluate the types of literature that researchers will encounter.
- iii. To convert the information of the search for a written document.
- iv. To help researchers learn how to search and analyze the right journal to submit.
- v. To promote their publication for further citation.

Outline

- 1. Introduce “Research Tools” Box,**
- 2. Developing a search strategy,**
- 3. Finding keyword and proper articles,**
- 4. Evaluate a paper/journal quality**
- 5. Keeping up-to-date (Alert system),**
- 6. The paraphrasing & editing tool**
- 7. Indexing desktop search tool and write an academic paragraph**
- 8. Avoid plagiarism,**
- 9. Reference management tools,**
- 10. Getting published, and**
- 11. Target suitable journal**
- 12. Q&A**

Research Tools Mind Map

**Developing a search strategy,
Finding keyword**

The Research Process

Source: <https://speakerdeck.com/vforrestal/beyond-the-citation-introducing-students-to-scholarly-research-and-writing-through-strategic-collaboration>

**Justify your
research**

Developing a search strategy

- » Defining the topic
- » Considering the scope of your topic
- » Identifying the main or important aspects
- » Compiling a list of keywords
- » Developing your search strategy
- It is important to develop a search strategy to, not only, find the information you need but to also clarify your topic.

How to Find and Develop a Viable Research Topic?

Step One: Identify a Topic.

Step Two: Test Your Topic.

Test the main concepts or keywords in your topic by looking them up in the appropriate background sources or by using them as search terms.

If you are finding too much information and too many sources, narrow your topic by using the **and** operator

Finding too little information may indicate that you need to broaden your topic.

Get found. Optimize your research articles for search engines.

Search engine optimization (SEO) of your journal articles is as important for you to do to market your research as it is for a company to market a retail product. Different markets and end users, but the same purpose and means. Thanks to companies like Google, SEO is almost obligatory if you would like to increase readership of your articles, increase citations and acknowledgment and to create an overall stronger academic visibility, both offline and online. By optimizing your articles, you guarantee that your articles are indexed and gain a higher *ranking* in general and academic search engines, such as Google and Google Scholar, Elsevier's Scirus, SciDiver, IEEE Xplore, PubMed, SciPlore.org, and more.¹

A higher ranking means that your article appears at the top of the list in the search results when someone types in one or more of the keywords or phrases you use in your article. The basis for this ranking varies from the search engine used to perform the search, as each search engine employs its own combination of algorithms based on the keywords, phrases, metadata and more contained in your document. Optimizing academic articles is also referred to as ASEO, or academic search engine optimization.²

Source: http://www.elsevier.com/data/assets/pdf_file/0017/145052/ECR_SEO_180912.pdf

Effective Use of Research & Publication Tools and
Resources ©2014 By: Nader Ale Ebrahim

Keywords

Selecting keywords lead to get more citation.

Google AdWords

ISI Web of
KNOWLEDGE
Transforming Research

MASTER KEYWORDS
LIST
Journal of International Business
Studies

Google Trends

Design Studies

KEYWORDS LIST

Choose up to five keywords for your paper from this list. You may substitute one keyword of your own choice not on this list.

aesthetics	environmental impact
architectural design	epistemology
artificial evolution	evaluation
automotive design	expert systems
built environment	facility programming
case based reasoning	generic design
case study/studies	graphic design
collaborative design	

MeSH (Medical Subject Headings)

Get found. Optimize your research articles for search engines.

TIPS:

▶ Write a good and short title for your article. If you can use one or more keywords in the title while accurately describing the content of your article, then do it. Keep in mind the audience of your article and any academic keywords specific to your field to inform which keywords may be best to use.

Source: http://www.elsevier.com/_data/assets/pdf_file/0017/145052/ECR_SEO_180912.pdf

MeSH Tree Structures for “Genes”

MeSH Tree Structures

[Genetic Phenomena \[G05\]](#)

[Genetic Structures \[G05.360\]](#)

[Genome \[G05.360.340\]](#)

[Genome Components \[G05.360.340.024\]](#)

[Attachment Sites, Microbiological \[G05.360.340.024.079\]](#)

[CpG Islands \[G05.360.340.024.159\]](#)

[DNA Sequence, Unstable \[G05.360.340.024.189\]](#) +

[DNA, Intergenic \[G05.360.340.024.220\]](#) +

▶ [Genes \[G05.360.340.024.340\]](#)

[Alleles \[G05.360.340.024.340.030\]](#)

[Gene Components \[G05.360.340.024.340.137\]](#) +

[Genes, cdc \[G05.360.340.024.340.220\]](#)

[Genes, Chloroplast \[G05.360.340.024.340.225\]](#)

[Genes, Developmental \[G05.360.340.024.340.230\]](#) +

[Genes, Dominant \[G05.360.340.024.340.240\]](#)

[Genes, Duplicate \[G05.360.340.024.340.250\]](#)

[Genes, Essential \[G05.360.340.024.340.270\]](#)

[Genes, Helminth \[G05.360.340.024.340.310\]](#)

[Genes, Immediate-Early \[G05.360.340.024.340.330\]](#)

[Genes, Immunoglobulin \[G05.360.340.024.340.335\]](#) +

[Genes, Insect \[G05.360.340.024.340.340\]](#)

Master Keywords List

The screenshot shows the website for the Journal of International Business Studies. At the top, the Palgrave Macmillan logo is on the left, and the journal title is in the center. On the right, there are links for Institutional Registration, Personal Registration, and Subscribe, along with Admin Login, My account, and E-alert sign up. Below the header is a search bar with a dropdown menu set to 'This journal' and a 'Go' button. A banner for the 'MASTERCARD FINANCE, PAYMENTS & E-COMMERCE CHAIR VACANCY' is displayed. The main content area is titled 'MASTER KEYWORDS LIST' and includes a navigation menu on the left, a central text block, and a right-hand sidebar with social media and service links.

Journal home > Master list of keywords

MASTER KEYWORDS LIST

- [Research methods](#)
- [Theories](#)
- [Topics](#)

The master keyword list is split into 3 main categories: research methods, theories, and topics. When choosing your keywords, please try to choose at least one keyword from each category.

RESEARCH METHODS [Top](#)

Data Source

- Primary
- Secondary

Research Design

- Comparative Thinking
- Construct Development and Evaluation
- Cross-Cultural Experiments
- Cross-Cultural Research/Measurement Issues
- Econometrics
- Equivalency

Journal home

Advance online publication

- About AOP

Current issue

Archive

- Decade Award
- Editorials - FREE
- Most Cited Articles - FREE
- JIBS Collections

Catalog entry

- Online submission
- Instructions for authors
- Palgrave Open
- About the Journal
- Statement of editorial policy
- Code of ethics
- Calls for papers
- Frequently asked questions
- Contact editorial team
- Subscribe

Sign up for e-alerts

Recommend this publication to your library

Receive RSS Web feeds

- About RSS Web feeds

Follow us on Twitter

Academy of International Business

JIBS/AIB Services

- AIB member log-in
- Adopt a Library

AIB resources

- AIB home
- Book reviews

Partners

- Academy of International Business

Google AdWords - Keyword Planner

Google AdWords

Home Campaigns Opportunities Tools and Analysis Billing My account

Keyword Planner Add ideas to your plan

Your product or service: Virtual Teams

Get ideas Modify search

Targeting: Malaysia, English, Google, Negative keywords

Customize your search: Keyword filters, Keyword options, Include/Exclude

Ad group ideas Keyword ideas

Download Add all (368)

Search terms	Avg. monthly searches	Competition	Suggested bid	Ad impr. share	Add to plan
virtual teams	30	Low	RM7.98	0%	»

1 - 1 of 1 keywords

Keyword (by relevance)	Avg. monthly searches	Competition	Suggested bid	Ad impr. share	Add to plan
virtual team	70	Low	-	0%	»
team building	1,600	High	RM2.11	0%	»
training and development	1,300	Medium	RM1.66	0%	»
teamwork	1,600	Low	RM0.13	0%	»
team building activities	1,300	High	RM1.43	0%	»
management skills	390	Medium	RM0.82	0%	»

Google AdWords – Keyword Like

The screenshot displays the Google AdWords Keyword Planner interface. At the top, there is a navigation bar with links for Home, Campaigns, Opportunities, Tools and Analysis, Billing, and My account. Below this, the 'Keyword Planner' section is active, showing 'Add ideas to your plan'. The search criteria include 'Your product or service' set to 'Virtual Teams'. The interface shows '1 of 22 ad group ideas' and an 'Add all (21)' button. A table of results is displayed, listing keywords like 'virtual team', 'training and development', and 'teamwork' with their respective search volumes, competition levels, and suggested bids.

Keyword (by relevance)	Avg. monthly searches	Competition	Suggested bid	Ad impr. share	Add to plan
virtual team	70	Low	-	0%	»
training and development	1,300	Medium	RM1.66	0%	»
teamwork	1,600	Low	RM0.13	0%	»
management skills	390	Medium	RM0.82	0%	»
virtual teams definition	10	Low	-	0%	»
cross functional team	110	Low	-	0%	»
teambuilding	210	Medium	RM1.58	0%	»
cross culture	70	Low	RM2.52	0%	»
teamwork games	90	Low	RM2.45	0%	»

Google AdWords - Keyword Output

Ad group	Keyword	Currency	Avg. monthly searches	Competition	Suggested Impr. shar	In account	In plan?
Seed Keywords	virtual teams	MYR	30	0.05	4.69	0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual team	MYR	70	0.04	1.39	0	N
Keyword Ideas	team building	MYR	1600	0.71	1.86	0	N
Keyword Ideas	teamwork	MYR	1600	0.12	0.46	0	N
Keyword Ideas	team building activities	MYR	1000	0.76	1.51	0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual teams definition	MYR	10	0.03		0	N
Keyword Ideas	cross functional team	MYR	110	0		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual team building	MYR	10	0.19		0	N
Keyword Ideas	cross culture	MYR	70	0.06		0	N
Keyword Ideas	team management	MYR	90	0.05		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual meeting	MYR	20	0.15	4.37	0	N
Keyword Ideas	types of teams	MYR	40	0.02		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual team definition	MYR	10	0.09		0	N
Keyword Ideas	self managed teams	MYR	30	0.01		0	N
Keyword Ideas	cultural sensitivity	MYR	40	0.02		0	N
Keyword Ideas	team bonding	MYR	30	0.22		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual work	MYR	20	0.11		0	N
Keyword Ideas	managing people in organization	MYR	10	0		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual team example	MYR	10	0.07		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual assistant jobs	MYR	20	0.44	0.09	0	N
Keyword Ideas	project team management	MYR	10	0.35		0	N
Keyword Ideas	global team	MYR	10	0		0	N
Keyword Ideas	project team development	MYR	10	0.11		0	N
Keyword Ideas	virtual jobs	MYR	10	0.23	0.65	0	N
Keyword Ideas	define business management	MYR	10	0.27		0	N
Keyword Ideas	managing virtual teams	MYR	10	0.08		0	N

Keywords Plus

- KeyWords Plus[®] are index terms created by Thomson Reuters from significant, frequently occurring words in the titles of an article's cited references.

Source: http://images.webofknowledge.com/WOK46/help/WOS/h_fullrec.html

KeyWords Plus® Creation Cycle

SAMPLE SOURCE RECORD

Title: Respiratory and immunological findings in brewery workers
Author(s): GodnicCvar J; Zuskin E; Mustajbegovic J; Schachter EN (REPRINT);
Kanceljak B; Macan J; Ilic Z; Ebling Z
Journal: AMERICAN JOURNAL OF INDUSTRIAL MEDICINE, 1999, V35, N1 (JAN), P 68-75
Author Keywords: brewery workers ; respiratory symptoms ; lung function ; immunology

Selected Cited References: (39 total, 14 shown for demonstration)

*WHO, 1986, P39, EARL DET OCC LUNG DI
BLASKI CA, 1996, V154, P334, AM J RESP CRIT CARE
HUY T, 1991, V144, P1314, AM REV RESPIR DIS
IVERSEN M, 1990, V20, P211, CLIN EXP ALLERGY
KORTEKANGASSAVO.O, 1993, V48, P147, ALLERGY
KORTEKANGASSAVO.O, 1994, V24, P836, CLIN EXP ALLERGY
MAESTRELLI P, 1992, V22, P103, CLIN EXP ALLERGY
MALMBERG P, 1986, V10, P316, AM J IND MED
MCCARTHY PE, 1985, V42, P106, BRIT J IND MED
MEZJAR B, 1989, P148, 14 INT C EUR AC ALL
REVSBECH P, 1990, V45, P204, ALLERGY
SHELDON JM, 1957, P507, MANUAL CLIN ALLERGY
SMID T, 1994, V25, P877, AM J IND MED
VIDAL C, 1995, V75, P121, ANN ALLERG ASTHMA

KeyWord Plus(R): ATOPIC-DERMATITIS PATIENTS; LUNG-FUNCTION;
GRAIN DUST; OCCUPATIONAL ASTHMA; MITE ALLERGY; STORAGE MITE; EXPOSURE;
HYPERSENSITIVITY; SYMPTOMS; DISEASE

ISI SOURCE DATABASE (1970-PRESENT)

No title available
The role of atopy in grain dust-induced airway disease
GRAIN DUST AND LUNG-FUNCTION - DOSE-RESPONSE RELATIONSHIPS
MITE ALLERGY AND EXPOSURE TO STORAGE MITES AND HOUSE DUST MITES IN FARMERS
SKIN PRICK TEST REACTIONS TO BREWERS-YEAST (SACCHAROMYCES-CEREVISIAE) IN ADULT ATOPIC-DERMATITIS PATIENTS
IMMEDIATE HYPERSENSITIVITY TO BAKERY, BREWERY AND WINE PRODUCTS IN YEAST-SENSITIVE ATOPIC-DERMATITIS PATIENTS
GUIDELINES FOR THE DIAGNOSIS OF OCCUPATIONAL ASTHMA
RELATIONSHIP BETWEEN SYMPTOMS AND EXPOSURE TO MOLD DUST IN SWEDISH FARMERS
LUNG-FUNCTION AFTER EXPOSURE TO BARLEY DUST
No title available
STORAGE MITE ALLERGY AMONG BAKERS
No title available
DUST-RELATED AND ENDOTOXIN-RELATED ACUTE **LUNG-FUNCTION** CHANGES AND WORK-RELATED **SYMPTOMS** IN WORKERS IN THE ANIMAL FEED-INDUSTRY
FOOD-INDUCED AND OCCUPATIONAL ASTHMA DUE TO BARLEY FLOUR

FREQUENTLY OCCURRING TITLE WORDS

ATOPIC-DERMATITIS PATIENTS
LUNG-FUNCTION
GRAIN DUST
OCCUPATIONAL ASTHMA
MITE ALLERGY

STORAGE MITE
EXPOSURE
HYPERSENSITIVITY
SYMPTOMS
DISEASE

Keywords and Keywords Plus®

Authors sometimes provide a list of keywords or terms that they feel best represent the content of their paper. These keywords are contained in the ISI record (1991 data forward, depending on the [database](#)) for each article and are searchable. In addition, ISI generates KeyWords Plus for many articles. **KeyWords Plus** are words or phrases that frequently appear in the titles of an article's references, but do not necessarily appear in the title of the article itself. KeyWords Plus may be present for articles that have no author keywords, or may include important terms not listed among the title, abstract, or author keywords.

Source: <http://wos.isitrial.com/help/helpdefs.html>

KeyWords Plus- Example-1

- New Product Development in Virtual Environment (ISI Indexed)
- Author Keywords: New product Development; Virtual teams; Concurrent Collaboration; Review paper
- KeyWords Plus: DEVELOPMENT TEAMS; PERFORMANCE; TECHNOLOGY; KNOWLEDGE; COMMUNICATION; PERSPECTIVE; INTEGRATION; INNOVATION; NETWORK; WORKING

Key Words Selection

TABLE 1: Search phrases used

Field	Search Strings
general/other	brain surgery – neurosurgery – hydrocephalus – peripheral nerve surgery
vascular	aneurysm surgery – arteriovenous malformation* – carotid endarterectomy – cavernous malformation – extracranial intracranial bypass – intracranial aneurysm* – [intracranial or intracerebral] and [hematoma or hemorrhage] – subarachnoid hemorrhage – vasospasm
tumor	brain tumor surgery – meningioma – glioblastoma* – glioma – meningioma – radiosurgery – radiotherapy
trauma	brain injury – coma – head injury – brain damage – spinal injury
functional	deep brain stimulation – epilepsy surgery – Parkinson's surgery – spinal cord stimulation – trigeminal neuralgia – stereotactic – stereotaxic – stereotaxy
spine	spine fusion – spine fixation – spine surgery – spinal surgery – spinal fusion – spinal fixation – [cervical or thoracic or lumbar] and [disc* or disk*]

* The asterisk was included in the search string as a wild card character. For example, the search “disc*” would return results for “disc” or “discs” or “discectomy.”

Source: Ponce, F. A., & Lozano, A. M. (2014). [Highly cited works in neurosurgery. Part II: the citation classics A review \(vol 112, pg 233, 2010\). Journal Of Neurosurgery 120\(5\), 1252-1257. doi: 10.3171/2014.2.JNS14358a](#)

Key Words Selection

Results: 26

(from Web of Science Core Collection)

You searched for:

TITLE: ("Envelope Design")

Timespan: All years. **Indexes:** SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH.

Results: 477

(from Web of Science Core Collection)

You searched for:

TITLE: (("efficiency envelope*") OR (envelope NEAR/5 building) OR (envelope NEAR/5 energy) OR ("envelope* energy* saving*") OR ("Envelope* System*") OR ("thermal* envelope*") OR ("Envelope* Design*"))

Timespan: All years. **Indexes:** SCI-EXPANDED, SSCI, A&HCI, CPCI-S, CPCI-SSH.

[Create Alert](#)**Refine Results**

Search within results for...

Web of Science Categories ▾

- MANAGEMENT (458)
- COMPUTER SCIENCE INFORMATION SYSTEMS (272)
- INFORMATION SCIENCE LIBRARY SCIENCE (177)
- BUSINESS (172)
- COMPUTER SCIENCE INTERDISCIPLINARY APPLICATIONS (118)

[more options / values...](#)Sort by: **Publication Date -- newest to oldest** ▾◀ Page of 122 Select Page ▾

1. **Leading Effective Global **Virtual Teams**: The Consequences of Methods of Communication**
By: Morgan, Lisa; Paucar-Caceres, Alberto; Wright, Gillian
SYSTEMIC PRACTICE AND ACTION RESEARCH Volume: 27 Issue: 6 Pages: 607-624 Published: DEC 2014

2. **Understanding the attitudes, knowledge sharing behaviors and task performance of core developers: A longitudinal study**
By: Licorish, Sherlock A.; MacDonell, Stephen G.
INFORMATION AND SOFTWARE TECHNOLOGY Volume: 56 Issue: 12 Special Issue: SI Pages: 1578-1596
Published: DEC 2014

3. **A Calibrated Group Decision Process**
By: Rokou, Elena; Kirytopoulos, Konstantinos
GROUP DECISION AND NEGOTIATION Volume: 23 Issue: 6 Special Issue: SI Pages: 1369-1384 Published: NOV 2014

4. **Satisfaction with outcome and process from web-based meetings for idea generation and**

[Analyze Results](#)[Create Citation Report](#)Times Cited: 0
*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*Times Cited: 0
*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*Times Cited: 0
*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*Times Cited: 0
(from Web of Science Core Collection)

Citation Report: 1218*(from Web of Science Core Collection)*You searched for: **TOPIC: ("virtual team**")** [...More](#)

This report reflects citations to source items indexed within Web of Science Core Collection. Perform a Cited Reference Search to include citations to items not indexed within Web of Science Core Collection.

Published Items in Each Year

The latest 20 years are displayed.
[View a graph with all years.](#)

Citations in Each Year

The latest 20 years are displayed.
[View a graph with all years.](#)

Results found: 1218

Sum of the Times Cited [?]: 15217

Sum of Times Cited without self-citations [?]: 10399

Citing Articles [?]: 8040

Citing Articles without self-citations [?]: 7210

Average Citations per Item [?]: 12.49

h-index [?]: 58

Finding proper articles

To be the best, cite the best

Citation analysis picks out new truth in Newton's aphorism that science 'stands on the shoulders of giants'.

The mass of medium-level research is less important for inspiring influential breakthroughs than the most highly-cited papers, a citation study argues.

Source: Corbyn, Z. (2010). [To be the best, cite the best. Nature 539. doi: doi:10.1038/news.2010.539](https://doi.org/10.1038/news.2010.539)

Research Quality Measures

Three key measures of research impact are:

- 1. Quality of the journal** – journal rankings, impact factors
- 2. Quality of the publication/article** = times cited as found in tools like Web of Science, Scopus and Google Scholar
- 3. Personal or departmental measure = *h*-index**

Source: <http://guides.library.vu.edu.au/content.php?pid=251876&sid=2079929>

Critically Analyzing Information Sources

1- Initial Appraisal:

Author

Date of Publication

Edition or Revision

Publisher

Title of Journal (Distinguishing Scholarly Journals from other Periodicals)

2- Content Analysis:

Intended Audience

Objective Reasoning

Coverage

Writing Style

Evaluative Reviews

h -index ([Jorge E. Hirsch](#))

- *A scientist has index h if h of [his/her] N_p papers have at least h citations each, and the other $(N_p - h)$ papers have at most h citations each.*

H-index from a plot of decreasing citations for numbered papers

H-index Example

Jorge E. Hirsch

Scholar A	Scholar B
10	27
10	12
9	5
8	4
7	4
6	2
6	2
56 citations	56 citations
6 h-index	4 h-index

A scientist has index h if h of his/her N_p papers have at least h citations each, and the other (N_p-h) papers have no more than h citations each.

As an example, a researcher with an H-index of 15 has (of their total number of publications) 15 papers which have been cited at least 15 times each.

Researcher A		Researcher B	
Paper rank	Citations	Paper rank	Citations
1	10	1	1348
2	8	2	159
3	6	3	50
4	5	4	4
5	4	5	4
6	0	6	3

Neither researcher can have an H-index of more than 6.

Source: <http://guides.is.uwa.edu.au/content.php?pid=372347&sid=3050052>

h-index importance

“Hirsch, who has a *h*-index of 49, says that a "**successful scientist**" will have an index of 20 after 20 years; an "**outstanding scientist**" will have an index of 40 after 20 years; and a "**truly unique individual**" will have an index of 60 after 20 years.”

Source: Ball, P. (2005). [Index aims for fair ranking of scientists](#). *Nature* 436(7053), 900-900.

Table 2: Publication and citation list of scientist S1

Rank (squared) - Publications	Citations	Sum
1 (1) A	20	20
2 (4) B	10	30
3 (9) C	9	39
4 (16) D	8	47
5 (25) E	6	53
6 (36) F	6	59
7 (49) G	6	65
8 (64) H	5	70
9 (81) I	5	75

Source: [Rousseau, Ronald. "New developments related to the Hirsch index." \(2006\).](#)

Publish or Perish

Publish or Perish is a free program that retrieves citations from Google Scholar and allows users to calculate:

- Total number of papers
- Total number of citations
- Average number of citations per paper
- Average number of citations per author
- Average number of papers per author
- Average number of citations per year
- Hirsch's h-index and related parameters
- The contemporary h-index
- The age-weighted citation rate
- Two variations of individual h-indices
- An analysis of the number of authors per paper

Source: <http://guides.library.vu.edu.au/content.php?pid=251876&sid=2079929>

Citation analysis

- Author impact analysis
- Journal impact analysis
- General citation search
- Multi-query center
- Web Browser

Program maintenance

Check for updates

Help resources

- Help contents
- What's new?
- 2-Minute introduction
- Frequently Asked Questions
- Version information
- Publish or Perish home page
- The Publish or Perish Book

Amazon customer review

is an excellent source for PhDs and junior scholars who are looking to forge links with other academics in the field to build their networks."

Open in browser...

Author impact | Journal impact | General citations | Multi-query center | Web Browser

Author impact analysis - Perform a citation analysis for one or more authors

Author's name:

Exclude these names:

Year of publication between: and:

- Biology, Life Sciences, Environmental Science
- Business, Administration, Finance, Economics
- Chemistry and Materials Science
- Engineering, Computer Science, Mathematics
- Medicine, Pharmacology, Veterinary Science
- Physics, Astronomy, Planetary Science
- Social Sciences, Arts, Humanities

- Lookup
- Lookup Direct
- Help

NOTE: Subject area selection is currently non-functional

Results

Papers:	419	Cites/paper:	141.05	h-index:	73
Citations:	59102	Cites/author:	52828.21	g-index:	242
Years:	238	Papers/author:	317.81	hc-index:	42
Cites/year:	248.33	Authors/paper:	1.91	hI,norm:	69

Lotfi A. Zadeh: all
 Query date: 2013-01-07
 Papers: 419
 Citations: 59102
 Years: 238

Cites	Per year	Rank	Authors	Title	Year	Publication	Publisher
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13522	329.80	1 LA Zadeh	Outline of a new approach to the analysis of comple...	1973	Systems, Man and Cybernet...	ieeexplore.ieee.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7254	186.00	14 LA Zadeh	The concept of a linguistic variable and its application...	1975	Information sciences	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	4826	109.68	17 RE Bellman, LA Z...	Decision-making in a fuzzy environment	1970	Management science	mansci.journal.informs.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1695	94.17	2 LA Zadeh	Fuzzy logic= computing with words	1996	Fuzzy Systems, IEEE Transa...	ieeexplore.ieee.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1638	38.09	3 LA Zadeh	Similarity relations and fuzzy orderings	1971	Information sciences	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1533	33.33	4 LA Zadeh	Probability measures of fuzzy events	1968	Journal of mathematical ana...	www-bisc.cs.berkeley.edu
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1455	28.53	29 LA Zadeh, CA De...	Linear System Theory:(The) State Space Approach	1963		citeulike.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1411	83.00	5 LA Zadeh	Toward a theory of fuzzy information granulation an...	1997	Fuzzy sets and systems	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1255	40.48	6 LA Zadeh	A computational approach to fuzzy quantifiers in nat...	1983	Computers & Mathematics w...	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1245	33.65	32 LA Zadeh	A Theory of Approximate Reasoning (AR).	1977		Electronics Research Labora...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1144	29.33	7 LA Zadeh	Fuzzy logic and approximate reasoning	1975	Synthese	Springer
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1143	43.96	33 LA Zadeh	Fuzzy logic	1988	Computer	ieeexplore.ieee.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1123	28.79	8 LA Zadeh	The concept of a linguistic variable and its application...	1975	Information sciences	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1029	26.38	9 LA Zadeh	The concept of a linguistic variable and its application...	1975	Information science	ci.nii.ac.jp
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	937	46.85	10 LA Zadeh	Fuzzy logic, neural networks, and soft computing	1994	Communications of the ACM	dl.acm.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	858	27.68	40 LA Zadeh	The role of fuzzy logic in the management of uncerta...	1983	Fuzzy sets and Systems	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	705	16.79	11 LA Zadeh	A fuzzy-set-theoretic interpretation of linguistic hedges	1972		Taylor & Francis
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	618	68.67	12 LA Zadeh	Toward a generalized theory of uncertainty (GTU)—...	2005	Information sciences	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	588	16.33	45 LA Zadeh	PRUF—a meaning representation language for natur...	1978	International Journal of Man...	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	575	71.88	13 I Guyon, S Gunn, ...	Feature extraction: foundations and applications	2006		books.google.com
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	465	23.25	15 LA Zadeh	Soft computing and fuzzy logic	1994	Software, IEEE	ieeexplore.ieee.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	420	6.56	53 LA Zadeh	Frequency analysis of variable networks	1950	Proceedings of the IRE	ieeexplore.ieee.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	407	9.47	16 LA Zadeh	Quantitative fuzzy semantics	1971	Information sciences	Elsevier

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General citation search - Perform a general citation search

Author(s):

Publication:

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Year of publication between: and:

Biology, Life Sciences, Environmental Science
 Business, Administration, Finance, Economics
 Chemistry and Materials Science
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Title words only

NOTE: Subject area selection is currently non-functional

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Results

Papers: 1000 Cites/paper: 151.56 h-index: 130
Citations: 151557 Cites/author: 122177.09 g-index: 370
Years: 42 Papers/author: 562.97 hc-index: 56
Cites/year: 3608.50 Authors/paper: 2.24 hI,norm: 97

analysis of complex systems and decision processes: all
Query date: 2013-01-07
Papers: 1000
Citations: 151557
Years: 42

Cites	Per year	Rank	Authors	Title	Year	Publication	Publisher
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	39481	4386.78	4	L Zadeh	2005	Logic, Thought and Action	Springer
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	13522	329.80	1	LA Zadeh	1973	Systems, Man and Cybernet...	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	7254	186.00	8	LA Zadeh	1975	Information sciences	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6829	325.19	127	JSR Jang	1993	Systems, Man and Cybernet...	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	6178	181.71	111	D DuBois, HM Prade	1980	Fuzzy sets and systems: theory and applications	books.google.cc
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3520	90.26	12	EH Mamdani, S Assil...	1975	International journal of man...	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	3162	632.40	811	TJ Ross	2009	Fuzzy logic with engineering applications	books.google.cc
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	2838	70.95	9	EH Mamdani	1974	... Engineers, Proceedings o...	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1695	94.17	271	LA Zadeh	1996	Fuzzy Systems, IEEE Transa...	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1535	80.79	345	JSR Jang, CT Sun	1995	Proceedings of the IEEE	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	1143	43.96	166	LA Zadeh	1988	Computer	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	891	38.74	424	S Keshav	1991	A control-theoretic approach to flow control	dl.acm.org
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	858	27.68	30	LA Zadeh	1983	Fuzzy sets and Systems	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	820	23.43	58	TJ Procyk, EH Mam...	1979	Automatica	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	774	48.38	132	S Loncaric	1998	Pattern recognition	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	767	36.52	14	JSR Jang, CT Sun	1993	Neural Networks, IEEE Tran...	ieeexplore.ieee.
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	762	26.28	26	M Sugeno	1985	Information sciences	Elsevier
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	639	16.82	7	HJ Zimmermann	1976	Description and optimization of fuzzy systems	Taylor & Francis
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	618	68.67	84	LA Zadeh	2005	Information sciences	Elsevier

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Check selection
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Uncheck 0 cites
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The Publish or Perish Book
Want to know more about citation analysis across disciplines? The Publish or Perish book reviews the evidence.
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Figure 1: Mean H-index Scores by Field of Study

[Source: Making Research Count: Analyzing Canadian Academic Publishing Cultures](#)

Advanced Search

Co-author (375)

- Ion Stoica
- Deborah Estrin
- Sylvia Ratnasamy
- Ramesh Govindan
- Lee Breslau

Academic > Author > Scott J. Shenker

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Scott J. Shenker University of California Berkeley [Edit](#)
 Publications: 479 | Citations: 34942 | G-Index: 183 | H-Index: 87
 Interests: Networks & Communications, Distributed & Parallel Computing, Operating Systems
 Collaborated with 375 co-authors from 1982 to 2010; Cited by 22343 authors
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Conference (41)

- SIGCOMM
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- IPTPS
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- CCR

Publication (479) [BibTeX](#) Order by: Year [View...](#)

[Delay scheduling: a simple technique for achieving locality and fairness in cluster scheduling](#) (Citations: 3)

Matei Zaharia, Dhruba Borthakur, Joydeep Sen Sarma, Khaled Elmeleegy, **Scott Shenker**, Ion Stoica
 Conference: EuroSys - EUROSYS, pp. 265-278, 2010

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Source: <http://guides.library.vu.edu.au/content.php?pid=251876&sid=2079929>

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Citation Report Distinct Author Summary: Zadeh, LA
 Timespan=All Years. Databases=SCI-EXPANDED, A&HCI, SSCI, CPCI-SSH, CPCI-S.

This report reflects citations to source items indexed within Web of Science. Perform a Cited Reference Search to include citations to items not indexed within Web of Science.

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Citations in Each Year

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Results found: 75
Sum of the Times Cited [?]: 5187
Sum of Times Cited without self-citations [?]: 5114
Citing Articles [?]: 4159
Citing Articles without self-citations [?]: 4130
Average Citations per Item [?]: 69.16
h-index [?]: 26

Results: **75**

Evaluate a paper/journal quality

Paper/journal quality

- Another guide to paper/journal quality is the general reputation of the association, society, or organization publishing the journal.
- Leading professional associations such as American Psychological Association (APA) or the Institute of Electrical and Electronics Engineers (IEEE) publish a range of journals that are highly regarded.

Web application to calculate the single publication h index

Web application to calculate the single publication *h* index (and further metrics) based on Google Scholar

by [Andreas Thor](#) (University of Leipzig, Germany) and [Lutz Bornmann](#) (Max Planck Society, Germany)

- 1 Search Google Scholar
- 2 Select **one** publication (you may additionally select duplicates)

virtual teams: a literature review

<input type="checkbox"/>	title	authors	year	citatio...
<input checked="" type="checkbox"/>	Virtual teams: a literature review	N Ale Ebrahim, S Ahmed, ...	2009	61
<input type="checkbox"/>	Virtual teams: a review of current literature and directions for future research	A Powell, G Piccoli, B Ives	2004	862
<input type="checkbox"/>	How do virtual teams process information? A literature review and implications f...	PL Curseu, R Schalk, I W...	2008	54
<input type="checkbox"/>	A typology of virtual teams implications for effective leadership	BS Bell, SWJ Kozlowski	2002	685
<input type="checkbox"/>	Implementing virtual teamworking. Part 1: a literature review of best practice	J Bal, PK Teo	2000	45
<input type="checkbox"/>	Managing virtual teams: A review of current empirical research	G Hertel, S Geister, U Kon...	2005	447
<input type="checkbox"/>	Virtual R&D teams in small and medium enterprises: A literature review	N Ale Ebrahim, S Ahmed, ...	2009	55
<input type="checkbox"/>	Bridging space over time: Global virtual team dynamics and effectiveness	ML Maznevski, KM Chudo...	2000	1211
<input type="checkbox"/>	Leadership in research and development organizations: A literature review and	T Elkina, DT Keller	2002	407

The single publication h index has been introduced by Schubert (2009) as the h-index calculated from the list of citing publications of one single publication.

Source: <http://labs.dbs.uni-leipzig.de/gsh/>

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- The **Institute for Scientific Information** (ISI) was founded by [Eugene Garfield](#) in 1960. It was acquired by [Thomson Scientific & Healthcare](#) in 1992, became known as **Thomson ISI** and now is part of the Healthcare & Science business of the multi-billion dollar [Thomson Reuters Corporation](#).
- ISI offered [bibliographic database](#) services. Its speciality: [citation indexing](#) and analysis, a field pioneered by Garfield. It maintains citation databases covering thousands of [academic journals](#), including a continuation of its long time print-based indexing service the [Science Citation Index](#) (SCI), as well as the [Social Sciences Citation Index](#) (SSCI), and the [Arts and Humanities Citation Index](#) (AHCI). All of these are available via ISI's [Web of Knowledge](#) database service.

Thomson Reuters (formerly ISI) has been the authority on citation data for over 50 years.

Eugene Garfield, Ph.D.

Founder & Chairman Emeritus
Institute for Scientific Information (ISI)

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The Institute for Scientific Information (ISI)

- The ISI also publishes annual [Journal Citation Reports](#) which list an [impact factor](#) for each of the journals that it tracks. Within the scientific community, journal impact factors play a large but controversial role in determining the kudos attached to a scientist's published research record.

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Thomson Reuters (formerly ISI)
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premier research platform for
information in the sciences,
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humanities.

Impact Factor

- The most commonly used measure of journal quality is Impact Factor. This is a number which attempts to measure the impact of a journal in terms of its influence on the academic community. Impact Factors are published by Thomson-ISI

Impact Factor and other bibliometric parameters

Impact Factor-Journal Ranking

- Relative impact factors are often a better guide to the importance of a journal than raw numbers. *JCR* allows you to compare the impact factors of different journals in the same subject area
- The *Economic History Review* has an impact factor of 1.051. At first glance, it would appear that this journal is relatively unimportant. In fact, it is arguably the premier English-language journal in its field (its major competitor, the *Journal of Economic History Review*, has an even lower impact factor: a mere 0.529!). Far more illuminating is the journal's relatively high impact factor compared to other journals in the history of the social sciences. *Economic History Review* ranks first out of 15 journals in the Thomson-ISI's list of journals in this sub-discipline.

Influences on Impact Factors: Subject Area

What are journal impact factors?

Impact factors are a measure of the "quality" of a journal - they identify the most frequently cited journals in a field.

Impact factors can be used to:

identify journals in which to publish

identify journals relevant to your research

confirm the status of journals in which you have published

The Impact factor formula

The impact factor of a journal is based on the average number of times that articles published in that journal in the two previous years (e.g. 2008 and 2009) were cited in the subsequent year (i.e. 2010). This is calculated using the following formula:

$$= \frac{\text{Cites in 2010 to items published in 2008 and 2009}}{\text{Number of items published in 2008 and 2009}}$$

If an impact factor is lower than 1.0 that means there were more articles published in the journal than there were cites to those articles in any given year.

Source: <http://guides.library.vu.edu.au/content.php?pid=251876&sid=2437240>

Be aware that...

- Many journals do not have an impact factor (sources other than JCR need to be consulted).
- The impact factor cannot assess the quality of individual articles.
- Only research articles, technical notes and reviews are “citable” items. Editorials, letters, news items and meeting abstracts are “non-citable items”.

→ Citations

 Source paper – published in 2006

 Cited reference – published in 2004 or 2005

$$\text{Impact Factor} = \frac{\text{Cites in 2006 to 2004 and 2005 papers}}{\text{Papers published in 2004 and 2005}}$$

The average number of citations in 2006 to scholarly material that was published in the prior two years

INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH

Impact Factor in 2008

Cites in 2008 to items published in:	2007 =	144	Number of items published in:	2007 =	278
	2006 =	280		2006 =	270
	Sum:	424		Sum:	548

Calculation: $\frac{\text{Cites to recent items}}{\text{Number of recent items}} = \frac{424}{548} = \mathbf{0.774}$

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Journal Citation Reports[®]

WELCOME HELP RETURN TO LIST PREVIOUS JOURNAL NEXT JOURNAL 2008 JCR Science Edition

Journal: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH

Mark	Journal Title	ISSN	Total Cites	Impact Factor	5-Year Impact Factor	Immediacy Index	Citable Items	Cited Half-life	Citing Half-life
<input type="checkbox"/>	INT J PROD RES	0020-7543	5900	0.774	1.380	0.132	325	9.0	9.8

[Cited Journal](#) [Citing Journal](#) [Source Data](#) [Journal Self Cites](#)

[CITED JOURNAL DATA](#) [CITING JOURNAL DATA](#) [IMPACT FACTOR TREND](#) [RELATED JOURNALS](#)

Journal Information

Full Journal Title: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH
ISO Abbrev. Title: Int. J. Prod. Res.
JCR Abbrev. Title: INT J PROD RES
ISSN: 0020-7543
Issues/Year: 18
Language: MULTI-LANGUAGE
Journal Country/Territory: ENGLAND
Publisher: TAYLOR & FRANCIS LTD
Publisher Address: 4 PARK SQUARE, MILTON PARK, ABINGDON OX14 4RN, OXON, ENGLAND
Subject Categories: ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL

EigenfactorTM Metrics
EigenfactorTM Score
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Article InfluenceTM Score
 0.360

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Journal Rank in Categories: [JOURNAL RANKING](#)

Journal Impact Factor

Cites in 2008 to items published in: 2007 = 144 Number of items published in: 2007 = 278
 2006 = 280 2006 = 270
 Sum: 424 Sum: 548
 Calculation: $\frac{\text{Cites to recent items}}{\text{Number of recent items}} = \frac{424}{548} = 0.774$

Impact Factor Trend Graph: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH
 Click on the "Return to Journal" button to view the full journal information.

**Impact Factor -- see below for calculations*

The journal impact factor is a measure of the frequency with which the "average article" in a journal has been cited in a particular year. The impact factor will help you evaluate a journal's relative importance, especially when you compare it to others in the same field. For more bibliometric data and information on this and other journal titles click on the "Return to Journal" button.

NOTE: Title changes and coverage changes may result in no impact factor for one or more years in the above graph.

2008 Impact Factor

Cites in 2008 to articles published in: 2007 = 144 Number of articles published in: 2007 = 278
 2006 = 280 2006 = 270
 Sum: 424 Sum: 548
 Calculation: $\frac{\text{Cites to recent articles}}{\text{Number of recent articles}} = \frac{424}{548} = 0.774$

2007 Impact Factor

Cites in 2007 to articles published in: 2006 = 88 Number of articles published in: 2006 = 270
 2005 = 204 2005 = 251
 Sum: 292 Sum: 521
 Calculation: $\frac{\text{Cites to recent articles}}{\text{Number of recent articles}} = \frac{292}{521} = 0.560$

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Journal: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH

Mark	Journal Title	ISSN	Total Cites	Impact Factor	5-Year Impact Factor	Immediacy Index	Citable Items	Cited Half-life	Citing Half-life
<input type="checkbox"/>	INT J PROD RES	0020-7543	5900	0.774	1.380	0.132	325	9.0	9.8

[Cited Journal](#) [Citing Journal](#) [Source Data](#) [Journal Self Cites](#)

[CITED JOURNAL DATA](#) [CITING JOURNAL DATA](#) [IMPACT FACTOR TREND](#) [RELATED JOURNALS](#)

Journal Information

Full Journal Title: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH
ISO Abbrev. Title: Int. J. Prod. Res.
JCR Abbrev. Title: INT J PROD RES
ISSN: 0020-7543
Issues/Year: 18
Language: MULTI-LANGUAGE
Journal Country/Territory: ENGLAND
Publisher: TAYLOR & FRANCIS LTD
Publisher Address: 4 PARK SQUARE, MILTON PARK, ABINGDON OX14 4RN, OXON, ENGLAND
Subject Categories: ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL

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EigenfactorTM Score
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Article InfluenceTM Score
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Journal Impact Factor

Cites in 2008 to items published in: 2007 = 144 Number of items published in: 2007 = 278
 2006 = 280 2006 = 270
 Sum: 424 Sum: 548
 Calculation: $\frac{\text{Cites to recent items}}{\text{Number of recent items}} = \frac{424}{548} = 0.774$

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Rank in Category: INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH

Journal Ranking ⓘ

For 2008, the journal **INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH** has an Impact Factor of **0.774**.

This table shows the ranking of this journal in its subject categories based on Impact Factor.

Category Name	Total Journals in Category	Journal Rank in Category	Quartile in Category
ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL	33	21	Q3
ENGINEERING, MANUFACTURING	38	21	Q3
OPERATIONS RESEARCH & MANAGEMENT SCIENCE	64	40	Q3

Category Box Plot ⓘ

For 2008, the journal **INTERNATIONAL JOURNAL OF PRODUCTION RESEARCH** has an Impact Factor of **0.774**.

This is a box plot of the subject category or categories to which the journal has been assigned. It provides information about the distribution of journals based on Impact Factor values. It shows median, 25th and 75th percentiles, and the extreme values of the distribution.

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Journals from: subject categories ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL [VIEW CATEGORY SUMMARY LIST](#)

Sorted by: Journal Title

Journals 1 - 20 (of 33) Page 1 of 2

 Impact Factor

Ranking is based on your journal and sort selections.

Mark	Rank	Abbreviated Journal Title <i>(linked to journal information)</i>	ISSN	JCR Data ⁱ⁾						Eigenfactor TM Metrics ^{j)}	
				Total Cites	Impact Factor	5-Year Impact Factor	Immediacy Index	Articles	Cited Half-life	Eigenfactor TM Score	Article Influence TM Score
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	APPL ERGON	0003-6870	1719	1.250	1.419	0.489	88	8.2	0.00333	0.404
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	CIRP ANN-MANUF TECHN	0007-8506	3771	1.123	1.514	0.094	149	>10.0	0.00474	0.307
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	COMPUT IND ENG	0360-8352	2389	1.057	1.637	0.209	139	9.0	0.00438	0.437
<input type="checkbox"/>	4	COMPUT OPER RES	0305-0548	3389	1.366	1.789	0.318	261	6.1	0.01317	0.673
<input type="checkbox"/>	5	ERGONOMICS	0014-0139	4167	1.604	1.729	0.110	127	>10.0	0.00525	0.436
<input type="checkbox"/>	6	IEEE IND APPL MAG	1077-2618	484	0.529	0.698	0.043	46	7.0	0.00144	0.306
<input type="checkbox"/>	7	IEEE T ENG MANAGE	0018-9391	1507	1.156	2.153	0.152	46	8.2	0.00312	0.655
<input type="checkbox"/>	8	IEEE T IND INFORM	1551-3203	227	2.356	2.565	0.286	28	2.6	0.00069	0.364
<input type="checkbox"/>	9	IIE TRANS	0740-817X	2656	1.023	1.373	0.144	90	>10.0	0.00659	0.673
<input type="checkbox"/>	10	IND MANAGE DATA SYST	0263-5577	720	0.945	1.237	0.042	72	5.0	0.00179	0.228
<input type="checkbox"/>	11	IND ROBOT	0143-991X	245	0.404	0.471	0.073	55	5.6	0.00068	0.110
<input type="checkbox"/>	12	INT J IND ENG-THEORY	1072-4761	131	0.123	0.257			6.4	0.00046	0.087
<input type="checkbox"/>	13	INT J IND ERGONOM	0169-8141	1288	0.760	0.995	0.071	99	8.3	0.00230	0.245
<input type="checkbox"/>	14	INT J PROD ECON	0925-5273	4733	2.026	2.767	0.344	358	5.9	0.01131	0.612
<input type="checkbox"/>	15	INT J PROD RES	0020-7543	5900	0.774	1.380	0.132	325	9.0	0.01042	0.360
<input type="checkbox"/>	16	ISSUES SCI TECHNOL	0748-5492	229	0.825	0.510	0.086	35	6.8	0.00111	0.255
<input type="checkbox"/>	17	J CONSTR ENG M ASCE	0733-9864	1410	0.564	0.954	0.048	103	7.7	0.00292	0.234

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Journal Summary List [Journal Title Changes](#)

Journals from: **subject categories ENGINEERING, INDUSTRIAL** [VIEW CATEGORY SUMMARY LIST](#)

Sorted by:

Journals 1 - 20 (of 33) Page 1 of 2

Total Cites *Ranking is based on your journal and sort selections.*

Mark	Rank	Abbreviated Journal Title <i>(linked to journal information)</i>	ISSN	JCR Data ⁱ						Eigenfactor TM Metrics ^j	
				Total Cites	Impact Factor	5-Year Impact Factor	Immediacy Index	Articles	Cited Half-life	Eigenfactor TM Score	Article Influence TM Score
<input type="checkbox"/>	1	J PROD INNOVAT MANAG	0737-6782	1832	2.650	3.607	0.121	33	9.5	0.00285	0.953
<input type="checkbox"/>	2	IEEE T IND INFORM	1551-3203	227	2.356	2.565	0.286	28	2.6	0.00069	0.364
<input type="checkbox"/>	3	INT J PROD ECON	0925-5273	4733	2.026	2.767	0.344	358	5.9	0.01131	0.612
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2. Virtual R&D teams and SMEs growth: A comparative study between Iranian and Malaysian SMEs	Ebrahim, N.A., Ahmed, S., Taha, Z.	2010	<i>African Journal of Business Management</i> , 4 (11) pp. 2368-2379.	0

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stances and offers related research propositions. The paper also discusses the role of the Internet in new product performance. Finally, the paper concludes with managerial and research implications.

1. New product development process and the role of the Internet

Past research has consistently shown that a high-quality new product development process is one of the most critical success factors in new product development [8,10–12]. As a result, it has offered numerous processes that firms can use when developing their new products. Cooper [13] defines a new product development process as a formal blueprint, roadmap, template or thought process for driving a new product project from the idea to market launch and beyond. The process involves predetermined set of stages and each stage consists of a set of prescribed, cross-functional and parallel activities. Each stage is preceded by a gate, controlling the flow of the process and providing a decision checkpoint in the process. Because of the stages and the

with the first and second-generation processes, the third-generation process emphasizes efficiency and effectiveness in the new product development process through four fundamental areas. First, it is fluid, which means that there are overlaps in stages for greater speed. Second, it involves fuzzy gates, reducing the rigidity of criteria used in the gates and allowing conditional or situational considerations of the activities. Third, it is more focused in terms of prioritizing projects. Finally, it is flexible, suggesting that each new product is unique and has its own unique development process [13].

There are also compelling issues that indicate that new product development process may not be uniform across firms and products. Takeuchi and Nanoka [14] argue that today's rapidly changing and competitive market conditions require firms to adopt a flexible and fast new product development process and that a holistic "rugby" style new product development might be needed to respond to the conditions. With this approach, new product teams move through all phases of the development together, passing the ball back and forth as they develop new products. Based on a case study, the authors concluded that it is possible to

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[Page 1 Paragraph 27]

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A small number of studies exclusively focused on the virtual R&D teams, *for example* [21-24] and none of them concentrated on the virtual R&D teams for NPD in SMEs. *Incomplete sentence* This paper summary the key findings of earlier works on different aspects of virtual R&D teams in SMEs and establishes it *the rationale a rationale* rationale in new product development (NPD). It highlights the gaps and weaknesses in the existing literature on virtual teams in R&D management and in new product development in SMEs. Finally, it identifies the future

developed under network cooperation, especially for high-tech industries [20].

A small number of studies exclusively focused on the virtual R&D teams, for example [21-24] and none of them concentrated on the virtual R&D teams for NPD in SMEs. This paper summary the key findings of earlier works on different aspects of virtual R&D teams in SMEs and establishes it rationale in new product development (NPD). It highlights the gaps and weaknesses in the existing literature on virtual teams in R&D management and in new product development in SMEs. Finally, it identifies the future research directions in the area of concern.

2-Review search methodology

Collaborative R&D activities involving SMEs has wide coverage. It applies to various activities ranging from information exchange to new products development. This review article is based on dependable and reputed publications. It mainly covers aspects like SMEs characteristics, scope of virtual R&D teams and their relationship in new product development (NPD). The articles are

Skip

We **reports** the relevant result of an online survey study.

Approve

We **report** the relevant result of an online survey study.

Abstract—In this paper, we present our more than two years research experiences on virtual R&D teams in small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) and draws conclusions, giving special attention to the structure of virtual teams required to support education-industry collaboration. We reports the relevant result of an online survey study. The online questionnaire was emailed by using the simple random sampling method to 947 manufacturing SMEs. The findings of this study show that SMEs in Malaysia and Iran are willing to use virtual teams for collaboration and the platform for industry-education collaboration is ready and distance between team members or differences in time zones, are not barriers to industry-education collaborations.

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Antimicrob Agents Chemother. 2009 Aug;53(8):3478-86

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Electrochemical Study of Structural Effects in Complexation of Nano-baskets: Calix[4]-1,2-crown-3, -crown-4, -crown-5, -crown-6

Bahram Mokhtari and Kohra Pourabdollah

Razi Chemistry Research Center (RCRC), Shahroze Branch, Islamic Azad University, Shahroze, I. R. Iran

Eight nano-baskets of calix[4]arene-1,2-crown-3, -crown-4, -crown-5, -crown-6 were synthesized and their binding abilities towards alkali and alkaline earth metals as well as some lanthanides were studied using differential pulse voltammetry. The novelty of this study was investigation of those macrocyclic complexes by voltammetric behaviors of two acidic molecules in each scaffold during complexation of crown ether ring. The results revealed that by increasing the binding ability of macrocycle amid carbon, the anodic oxidation peak of carboxylic acids was decreased. Moreover, the

calix[4]arene-1,2-crown-6. Combining crown ethers with calix[4]arenes increases the cation binding ability of the parent calixarenes and control of the selectivity is obtained through modulation of the crown ether size. Attachment of proton-recognizable groups to calixarenes can further improve their extraction properties because the ionized group not only participates in metal ion coordination, but also eliminates the need to transfer aqueous phase ligands into the organic phase. Ungard et al.^[1] reported the first di-proton-recognizable calix[4]crown-5 in

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Potential user factors driving adoption of IPTV: What are customers expecting from IPTV?

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Reading, PA 19610-6009, USA

Received 4 December 2005; received in revised form 1 May 2006; accepted 8 May 2006

Abstract

Internet Protocol Television (IPTV), the convergence services of television and Internet, is being rapidly developed around the world. The advent of digital technologies has changed the convergence market dramatically with the wide diffusion of the convergent services. Using the Technology Acceptance Model as a conceptual framework and method of logistic regression, this research analyzes the demand for IPTV by drawing data from 452 consumers. Individuals' responses to questions about whether they accept IPTV are collected and combined with observations of their socio-economic characteristics and intrinsic/extrinsic factors modified from the Technology Acceptance Model. Results of logistic regression show two variables (intrinsic and extrinsic factors) that seem to explain what influences consumer behavior towards adopting IPTV. Overall, the logistic regression model explains over 50% of the variance in IPTV adoption. The variances shed light on the multi-open platform environment that IPTV will forge.

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Keywords: IPTV; User analysis; Logistic model; South Korea

1. Introduction

Recent development of IT and media technologies have given a tremendous push toward the development of convergence services like Digital Multimedia Broadcasting (DMB) and IPTV (Internet Protocol Television). Korea has been taking a leadership role in developing not only IPTV, but also the

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Effect of ST3GAL 4 and FUT 7 on sialyl Lewis X synthesis and multidrug resistance in human acute myeloid leukemia

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ABSTRACT

Sialyl Lewis X (sLe X, CD15s) is a key antigen induced on tumor cell surfaces during multidrug resistance (MDR) development. The present study investigated the effect of α 1, 3-fucosyltransferase VII (FucT VII) and α 2, 3-sialyltransferase IV (ST3Gal IV) on sLe X oligosaccharide synthesis as well as their impact on MDR development in acute myeloid leukemia cells (AML). FUT7 and ST3GAL4 were overexpressed in three AML MDR cells and bone marrow mononuclear cells (BMNCs) from AML patients with MDR by real-time polymerase chain reaction (PCR). A close association was found between the expression levels of FUT7 and ST3GAL4 and the amount of sLe X oligosaccharides, as well as the phenotypic evaluation of MDR of HL60 and HL60/ADR cells both in vitro and in vivo. Manipulation of the two genes' expression modulated the activity of phosphoinositide-3 kinase (PI3K)/Akt signaling pathway, probably by regulating the proportionally mutative expression of P-glycoprotein (P-gp) and multidrug resistance related protein 1 (MRP1), both of which are known to be involved in MDR. Blocking the PI3K/Akt pathway by specific inhibitor LY294002 or Akt short hairpin RNA (shRNA) resulted in the reduced MDR of HL60/ADR cells. Our study indicated that sLe X involved in the development of MDR of AML cells probably through FUT7 and ST3GAL4 by regulating the activity of PI3K/Akt signaling pathway and the expression of P-gp and MRP1.

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1. Introduction

Acute myeloid leukemia (AML), the most common type of leukemia in adults, has the lowest survival rate among all leukemias [1]. It is a clonal malignancy of the hematopoietic system characterized by accumulation of immature cell population in the bone marrow or peripheral blood [2]. Multidrug resistance (MDR) is a major challenge to the successful treatment of AML. Classic MDR is the consequence of overexpression of transporter proteins belonging to the ATP binding cassette (ABC) family, such as P-gp and MRP1, which lead to lower intracellular drug accumulation and reduce cellular toxicity of chemotherapeutic agents [3]. However, many researchers are managing to

adequately evaluate the interaction of glycan alterations and resistance to chemotherapy of neoplastic cells so as to understand their pathogenesis. However, there is still little information about the role of glycosyltransferases and relevant glycogenes in the development of AML MDR except the modification of glycan structures has been observed in drug-resistance leukemia cells [4,5].

Glycosylation is one of the most important modifications of proteins and lipids [6]. Alterations in cell surface glycosylation are acknowledged as a hallmark of carcinogenesis which usually leads to the expression of tumor-associated carbohydrate antigens (TACAs) on glycoproteins or glycolipids that decorate cell surfaces [7]. Lewis antigens are functionally important terminal glycan epitopes, which are usually subdivided into two groups: types 1 and 2, depending on whether the terminal galactose is bound to the preceding GlcNAc by β -1, 3-galactosyltransferases (Gal-T) or β -1, 4 Gal-T [8]. All type 1 structures contain a α 1, 4-Fuc residue on the GlcNAc catalyzed by α 1, 4-FucTs such as Le^x, sLe^x and Le^s. It is the same for type 2 antigens including Le X, sLe X and Le Y, but the linkage is α 1, 3 instead (catalyzed by products of FUT3 through -7 and FUT9) [9].

Sialyltransferases (STs) catalyzed the transformation of sialic acid residues from donor substrate CMP-sialic acid to the oligosaccharide side chains of glycoconjugates. Different STs showing cell and tissue tropism are unique in substrate specificities and in types of linkage formed

Abbreviations: STs, sialyltransferases; FucTs, fucosyltransferases; MDR, multidrug resistance; PCR, polymerase chain reaction; PI3K, phosphoinositide-3 kinase; P-gp, P-glycoprotein; MRP1, multidrug resistance related protein 1; shRNA, short hairpin RNA; ADR, adriamycin; BMNC, bone marrow mononuclear cells; PBS, phosphate buffered saline; PI3K, PI3K-containing 0.1% Tween 20; DMEM, Dulbecco's modified Eagle's medium; AML, acute myeloid leukemia; CML, chronic myeloid leukemia.

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E-mail address: ljun@dmu.edu.cn (L. Jun).

¹ Hongye Ma and Huimin Zhou contributed equally to this work.

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Electrochemical Study of Structural Effects in Complexation of Nano-baskets: Calix[4]-1,2-crown-3, -crown-4, -crown-5, -crown-6

Bahram Mokhtari and Kobra Pourabdollah

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Eight nano-baskets of calix[4]arene-1,2-crown-3, -crown-4, -crown-5, -crown-6 were synthesized and their binding abilities towards alkali and alkaline earth metals as well as some lanthanides were studied using differential pulse voltammetry. The novelty of this study was investigation of those macrocyclic complexes by voltammetric behaviors of two acidic moieties in each scaffold during complexation of crown ether ring. The results revealed that by increasing the binding ability of macrocycle and cation, the anodic oxidation peak of carboxylic acids was decreased. Moreover, the

calix[4]crowns lag far behind. Combining crown ethers with calix[4]arenes increases the cation binding ability of the parent calixarenes, and control of the selectivity is obtained through modulation of the crown ether size. Attachment of proton-ionizable groups to calixcrowns can further improve their extraction properties because the ionized group not only participates in metal ion coordination, but also eliminates the need to transfer aqueous phase anions into the organic phase. Ungaro et al.^[9] reported the first di-proton-ionizable calix[4]crown-5 in

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Retraction: Retraction notice

It has been brought to the attention of the PLOS ONE editors that substantial parts of the text in this article were appropriated from text in the following publications:

Identification and biochemical characterization of small-molecule inhibitors of Clostridium botulinum neurotoxin serotype A.

Roxas-Duncan V, Enyedy I, Montgomery VA, Eccard VS, Carrington MA, Lai H, Gul N, Yang DC, Smith LA.

Antimicrob Agents Chemother. 2009 Aug;53(8):3478-86

Eubanks LM, Hixon MS, Jin W, Hong S, Clancy CM, et al. (2007) An in vitro and in vivo disconnect uncovered through high-throughput identification of botulinum neurotoxin A antagonists. Proc Natl Acad Sci USA 104: 2602–2607.

PLOS ONE therefore retracts this article due to the identified case of plagiarism. PLOS ONE apologizes to the authors of the publications above and to the readers. ([comment on this retraction](#))

Clinics

Hospital das Clinicas da Faculdade de Medicina da Universidade de Sao
Paulo

THIS ARTICLE HAS BEEN RETRACTED. See Clinics (Sao Paulo). 2013

October; 68(10): 1382.

An overview of recently published medical papers in Brazilian scientific journals

Mauricio Rocha e Silva and Ariane Gomes

[Additional article information](#)

Abstract

Full Length Research Paper

Computational study of environmental fate of ionic liquids using conductor-like screening model for real solvents (COSMO-RS) method

Zakari, A. Y., Waziri, S. M., Aderemi, B. O. and Mustapha, S. I.*

Department of Chemical Engineering, Ahmadu Bello University Zaria, Nigeria.

The COSMO-RS method is an advanced method for the quantitative calculation of solvation mixture thermodynamics based on quantum chemistry. It was developed by Andreas Klamt and is distributed as the software COSMOtherm by his company COSMOlogic (as well as in the form of several remakes by others).

Some Nigerian researchers have used the software (without a license) and report a tremendously and completely unbelievably good correlation ($r^2=0.992$) between the predicted results and experimental data for the logKow (octanol water partition coefficient) of ionic liquids.

Penalty for Plagiarism

Outside of academia the problem of plagiarism continues to generate headlines and scandals for politicians. In Germany, two prominent cabinet members have been forced to step down due to allegations of plagiarism in their doctoral dissertations. Meanwhile, in Canada, the head of the nation's largest school district was forced to resign in the face of plagiarism allegations, and plagiarism scandals have also embroiled a senator in the Philippines, the prime minister of Romania, and several members of the Russian Duma.

Source: J. Bailey. "Defending Against Plagiarism, Publishers need to be proactive about detecting and deterring copied text.," 26 November; <http://www.the-scientist.com/?articles.view/articleNo/35677/title/Defending-Against-Plagiarism/>.

PubPeer strikes again: Leukemia paper retracted for image duplications

In July, a PubPeer commenter called out a paper in *Biochimica et Biophysica Acta* for image duplication; by September, the paper was retracted for the exact reason detailed in the anonymous comment.

Here's the [notice](#) for "Effect of ST3GAL 4 and FUT 7 on sialyl Lewis X synthesis and multidrug resistance in human acute myeloid leukemia," a paper initially published in June:

“ This article has been retracted at the request of the authors. It contained several inappropriate-ly processed and incorrect Figures. On behalf of all authors, the corresponding author has taken full responsibility and apologizes to the readers of BBA Molecular Basis of Disease for submitting and publishing the erroneous article and any inconvenience caused.

An anonymous PubPeer commenter compiled the following criticism ([click here or on the picture below for a larger image](#)):

“ Concern about Figures 3, 5, and 7:
Several of the immunohistochemistry staining panels shown in Figures 3, 5, and 7 represent different experimental conditions, but appear to show overlapping areas and/or are very similar when flipped.

Here is a figure showing my concerns: <http://i.imgur.com/ZTFVUxP.jpg>

Retraction Watch

Leukemia paper retracted for plagiarism — 18 years later

with 2 comments

Nearly two decades after a Polish researcher plagiarized the work of a Turkish team, her theft has been exposed and the paper retracted.

According to an article in Polish-language paper [Gazeta Wyborcza](#), [Jolanta Rzymowska](#) of the Medical University of Lublin was the subject of two disciplinary hearings, the first in February 2014, following the discovery of her plagiarism by well-known Polish fraud hunter [Marek Wronski](#). It was determined that her 1996 paper contained word-for-word text from a paper by a team at the University of Ankara.

Ultimately, Rzymowska was given an official reprimand, rather than any harsher disciplinary action, because she copied descriptions rather than results. From a Google translation of the [article](#):

“ The Commission concluded that the results are the most important element of intellectual property and the descriptive part is much less important.

Here's the [notice](#):

“ The Acting Editor in Chief of Biological Trace Element Research retracts the following article: Rzymowska, Magnesium and Iron Contents of Leukemic Lymphocytes in Acute Leukemias and [Hemolytic Anemia](#), June 1996, Volume 53, Issue 1–3, DOI 10.1007/BF02784559.

This full retraction is due to the author's having used – without permission – significant amounts of

Tracking retractions as a window into the scientific process

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Retraction Watch

Publisher discovers 50 manuscripts involving fake peer reviewers

with 23 comments

BioMed Central has uncovered about fifty manuscripts in their editorial system that involved fake peer reviewers, Retraction Watch has learned.

Most of the cases were not published because they were discovered by a manuscript editor on a final pre-publication check. The five or so that have been published will go through some sort of re-review, which may result in expressions of concern or retraction.

The narrative seems similar to that in the growing number of cases of [peer review manipulation](#) we've seen recently. What tipped off the editor was minor spelling mistakes in the reviewers' names, and odd non-institutional email addresses that were often changed once reviews had been submitted, in an apparent attempt to cover the fakers' tracks. Those "reviewers" had turned in reports across several journals, spanning several subjects.

It would seem that a third party, perhaps marketing services helping authors have papers accepted, was involved.

The publisher has let all of its external editors in chief know about the situation. To prevent it from happening again, authors will not be able to recommend reviewers for their papers. Here's a message from BioMed Central senior managing editor Diana Marshall that went out to a number of journal editors earlier today: [Read the rest of this entry »](#)

To me

Cat Ferguson posted: " Two papers by an overlapping group of researchers in Italy have been retracted for manipulated figures. In late 2013, perennial tipster Clare Francis sent their concerns about several papers, including the two that have been retracted, by authors who f"

New post on **Retraction Watch**

Cut and paste and a PC crash: figure manipulations sink two papers

by [Cat Ferguson](#)

Two papers by an overlapping group of researchers in Italy have been retracted for manipulated figures. In late 2013, perennial tipster Clare Francis sent their concerns about several papers, including the two that have been retracted, by authors who frequently publish together. One of the papers, in the Journal of Neurochemistry, is from a team led by Ferdinando Nicoletti; four other [...]

We use plagiarism Detection

The screenshot shows the 'Instructions for authors' page for the Journal of the Operational Research Society. The page lists various research areas: Training, Transport, Travelling salesman, Urban studies, Vehicle routing, and Water. It prominently features the COPE (Committee on Publication Ethics) logo and a badge for iThenticate plagiarism detection. A text box states: 'This journal is a member of and subscribes to the principles of the [Committee on Publication Ethics](#).' The footer includes the journal's ISSN (0160-5682) and EISSN (1476-9360), along with links to 'About Palgrave Macmillan', 'Contact Us', 'Legal Notice', 'Privacy Policy', 'Accessibility Statement', 'RSS Web feeds', and 'Help'. Copyright information for 2011 is provided, mentioning Palgrave Macmillan as a division of Macmillan Publishers Limited, and listing partners: INASP, JDP, CrossRef, COUNTER, COPE, and iThenticate.

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How do I avoid plagiarism?

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- indicate whether you have downloaded information from the Internet.
- never use someone else's electronic storage media, artwork, pictures or graphics as if it were your own.
- never copy directly without crediting the source
- do not translate without crediting the source
- do not paraphrase someone else's work without crediting the source
- do not piece together sections of the work of others into a new whole
- do not resubmit your own or other's previously graded work
- do not commit collusion (unauthorised collaboration, presenting work as one's own independent work, when it has been produced in whole or in part in collusion with other people)
- ghost-writing – you should not make use of ghost writers or professional agencies in the production of your work or submit material which has been written on your behalf

10 Major source of plagiarism

1. **Replication:** Submitting a paper to multiple publications in an attempt to get it published more than once
2. **Duplication:** Re-using work from one's own previous studies and papers without attribution
3. **Secondary Source:** Using a secondary source, but only citing the primary sources contained within the secondary one
4. **Misleading Attribution:** Removing an author's name, despite significant contributions; an inaccurate or insufficient list of authors who contributed to a manuscript
5. **Invalid Source:** Referencing either an incorrect or nonexistent source
6. **Paraphrasing:** Taking the words of another and using them alongside original text without attribution
7. **Repetitive Research:** Repeating data or text from a similar study with a similar methodology in a new study without proper attribution
8. **Unethical Collaboration:** Accidentally or intentionally use each other's written work without proper attribution; when people who are working together violate a code of conduct
9. **Verbatim:** copying of another's words and works without providing proper attribution, indentation or quotation marks
10. **Complete:** Taking a manuscript from another researcher and resubmitting it under one's own name

Source: [iThenticate \(2013\) SURVEY SUMMARY | Research Ethics: Decoding Plagiarism and Attribution in Research](#)

Least Common Forms of Plagiarism and Attribution Issues in Research

Least Common Forms of Plagiarism and Attribution Issues in Research

Source: [iThenticate \(2013\) SURVEY SUMMARY | Research Ethics: Decoding Plagiarism and Attribution in Research](#)
Effective Use of Research & Publication Tools and
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 John Zarocostas (2007)
 BMJ (Clinical research ed.) 334 (7587) p. 225
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- New-generation diabetes management: glucose sensor-augmented insulin pump therapy.
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 Expert review of medical devices 8 (4) p. 449-58
<http://www.pubmedcentral.nih.gov/articlerender.fcgi?artid...>
- New-generation diabetes management: glucose sensor-augmented insulin pump therapy.
 Eda Cengiz, Jennifer L Sherr, Stuart A Weinzimer, William V Tamborlane (2011)
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References

Citing references

- Word and OpenOffice plug-in
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Tools

Small and medium enterprises (SMEs) are the driving engine behind economic growth [1].

References

- [1] N. Ale Ebrahim, S. Ahmed, and Z. Taha, "Virtual R & D teams in small and medium enterprises: A literature review," *Scientific Research and Essay*, vol. 4, pp. 1575–1590, December 2009.

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Getting published

Paper Structure

- Title
- Affiliation
- Abstract
- Keywords
- Nomenclatures
- Introduction
- Materials and methods
- Results and Discussions
- Conclusions
- References

We often write in the following order:

- Figures and Tables
- Materials and Methods
- Results and Discussion
- Conclusions
- Introduction
- Abstract and Title

Source: [How to Write a World Class Paper, From title to references, From submission to revision Forum Scientum Workshop, 2011-8-22](#)

[Presented By: Anthony P F Turner and Alice Tang Turner Editor-In-Chief and Managing Editor, Biosensors & Bioelectronics](#)

Writing your literature review

Writing your literature review takes time. You may need to complete several drafts before your final copy. It is important to have a good introduction that clearly tells the reader what the literature will be about.

An introduction must tell the reader the following:

- **what you are going to cover in the review**
- **the scope of your research**
- **how the review ties in with your own research topic.**

Source: https://www.dlsweb.rmit.edu.au/lsu/content/2_AssessmentTasks/assess_tuts/lit_review_LL/writing.html

Introduction

This is a good example of an introduction because it has a topic sentence which indicates what will be covered and also tells the reader the specific focus of the literature review in the concluding sentence.

Topic sentence - identifies five major themes as the scope of this review

Many theories have been proposed to explain what motivates human behaviour. **Although the literature covers a wide variety of such theories, this review will focus on five major themes which emerge repeatedly throughout the literature reviewed.** These themes are: incorporation of the **self-concept** into traditional theories of motivation, the influence of **rewards** on motivation, the increasing importance of **internal forces** of motivation, **autonomy and self-control** as sources of motivation, and **narcissism** as an essential component of motivation. **Although the literature presents these themes in a variety of contexts, this paper will primarily focus on their application to self-motivation.**

5 major themes to be covered

Concluding sentence - specific focus

Paragraphs

A paragraph is a group of connected sentences that develop a single point, argument or idea. Paragraphs need to link to other paragraphs so that the themes, arguments or ideas developed are part of a coherent whole rather than separate bits.

A paragraph should include:

- **a main statement / idea that you are putting forward, ie topic sentence**
- **evidence from research to support / argue your idea, showing where the writers agree and / or disagree**
- **student analysis of the research literature where appropriate**
- **summing up and linking to the next idea (paragraph).**

In the literature review, you will need to show evidence of integrating your readings into each paragraph and analysis of the readings where necessary.

Source: https://www.dlsweb.rmit.edu.au/lisu/content/2_AssessmentTasks/assess_tuts/lit_review_LL/writing.html

Integrating arguments in paragraphs

Integration of multiple sources

To develop an integrated argument from multiple sources, you need to link your arguments together. The model below is a guide.

Topic sentence - outlining your main claim or key point for that paragraph

Most early theories of motivation were concerned with need satisfaction. Robbins, Millett, Cacioppe and Waters-Marsh (1998) argued that motivation relies on what a person needs and wants. Similarly the early theories of Maslow and McGregor (Robbins et al. 1998) focused on personal needs satisfaction as the basis for motivational behaviour. However, recent studies outlined by Leonard, Beauvais, and Scholl (1999) suggest that personality and disposition play an equally important role in motivation. Current thinking does not discount these theories, but simply builds on them to include a self-concept.

Supporting evidence from the readings

Contrasting theories from research

Concluding sentence - linking to the next paragraph

Integrating arguments in paragraphs

Integration of student analysis

It is important to integrate your analysis and interpretation of the literature in your literature review. Read the following paragraph and see how the arguments have been integrated into the paragraph along with student analysis. Analysis is not just student opinion, it needs to be supported by the literature.

Topic sentence - outlining your main claim or key point for that paragraph

First statement of evidence from the literature

By its very nature, motivation requires a degree of individual satisfaction or narcissism. Robbins, Millet, Cacioppe, and Waters-Marsh (1998) suggest that motivation has as its very basis the need to focus on, and please the self. This is supported by Shaw, Shapard and Waugaman (2000) who contend that this narcissistic drive is based on the human effort to find personal significance in life. It can be argued that the desire to improve one's status is a highly motivational force, and is central to the idea of narcissistic motivation. The narcissistic motivational strategies put forward by Shaw et al. (2000) are concerned with motivation for life in general, but may also have applications in the context of work. These strategies, with their focus on personal needs, demonstrate that narcissism is an essential component of motivation.

Second statement of evidence from the literature

Student analysis

Concluding statement

Discussion Article Template

Discussion Article Title

By: _____ ← **BY-LINE**

— INTRODUCTION —

↖ **PROVIDE CONTEXT FOR AN AREA OF DISCUSSION IN YOUR NICHE**

— BODY —

↖ **EXPLAIN ONE SIDE OF A DISCUSSION**

— BODY —

↖ **BALANCE THE ARTICLE WITH A COUNTER POINT TO THE ORIGINAL DISCUSSION**

— CONCLUSION —

↖ **USE BOTH SIDES OF THE DISCUSSION TO PICK THE "RIGHT" ANSWER AND EXPLAIN WHY**

— RESOURCE BOX —

Suggest (that)	Recent studies outlined by Leonard et al (1999) suggest that personality and disposition play an equally important role in motivation.
Argue (that)	Leonard et al (1999) argue that there are three elements of self perception.
Contend(s)	Mullens (1994) contends that motivation to work well is usually related to job satisfaction.
Outline	Recent studies outlined by Mullins (1994) suggest that personality and disposition play an equally important role in motivation.
Focus on	The early theories of Maslow and McGregor (Robbins et al, 1998) focused on personal needs and wants as the basis for motivation.
Define(s)	Eunson (1987, p. 67) defines motivation as 'what is important to you'.
Conclude(s) (that)	Reviewing the results of the case study, Taylor (1980) concludes that the theories of job enrichment and employee motivation do work.
State	He further states that there is an increasing importance on the role of autonomy and self regulation of tasks in increasing motivation.
Maintains (that)	Mullins (1994) maintains that job enrichment came from Herzber's two factor theory.
Found (that)	Mullins (1994) found that there is an increasing importance on the role of autonomy and self regulation of tasks in improving motivation.
Promote(s)	This promotes the idea that tension and stress are important external sources of motivation, which can be eliminated by completing certain tasks.
Establish(ed) (by)	As established by Csikszentmihalyi (Yair 2000, p. 2) 'the more students feel in command of their learning, the more they fulfil their learning potential'.
Asserts (that)	Locke's Goal Setting Theory asserts that setting specific goals tends to encourage work motivation (Robbins et al, 1998).
Show(s)	Various theories of motivation show employers that there are many factors that influence employees work performance.
Claim(s) (that)	Hackman and Oldham (1975) claim that people with enriched jobs, and high scores on the Job Diagnostic Survey, experienced more satisfaction and motivation.
Report(s)	Mullins (1994) reports on four content theories of motivation.
Mention(s)	Mullins (1994) mentions two common general criticisms of Herzberg's theory.
Address	Redesigning jobs so that responsibility moved from supervisors to the workers, was an attempt to address the issues of job satisfaction (Mullins, 1994).

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Preparing for Submission

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IF	12.367
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- The annual Journal Citation Report Impact Factor is a ratio between citations and recent citable items published. Thus, the impact factor of a journal is calculated by dividing the number of current year citations by the source items published in that journal during the previous two years.
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